

Integrated Renewable Production of Sorbitol and Xylitol from Switchgrass

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Abstract.

This work deals with the design of integrated facilities for the production of xylitol and sorbitol from lignocellulosic biomass. Xylitol can be obtained from xylose via fermentation or catalytic hydrogenation. Sorbitol is obtained from glucose, but preferably from fructose, also via fermentation or catalytic hydrogenation. Fructose can be obtained from glucose via isomerization. Thus, a superstructure of alternatives is formulated to process switchgrass, corn stover, miscanthus, and others agricultural and forestry residues. Different pretreatments, such as dilute acid or AFEX for the fractionation of the biomass are evaluated. Next, after hydrolysis, the C5 and C6 sugars are processed separately for which a catalytic or a fermentation stage are considered. Glucose is to be isomerized before it can be processed. Finally, crystallization in a multistage evaporator system is used for purification. The optimization of the system suggests the use of dilute acid and the catalytic system. A system of 3 crystallizers is selected. For a facility that produces 145 kt/yr of xylitol and 157.6 kt/yr of sorbitol, the investment adds up to 120.74 M€ for a production cost of 0.28 €/kg of products. The inverse engineering of biomass was also performed resulting in a composition of 15% water, 20% cellulose, 40% hemicellulose, 15% lignin and 5% ash. The closest biomass corresponds to *Sargassum* (brown algae), that is capable of producing 230.5 kt/yr of xylitol and 116 kt/yr of sorbitol with investment and production costs of 120.5 M€ and of 0.25 €/kg of products, respectively.

Keywords: Biorefinery, process and product design, superstructure optimization

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1. Introduction

The chemical industry is undergoing a transformation towards a more sustainable future starting from the use of renewable instead of fossil resources, which constitutes the 7th principle of green chemistry¹. Biomass has emerged as a rich raw material towards the production of energy and chemicals². While energy and fuels focused the first efforts of biorefineries design, such as first and second generation bioethanol,^{3,4} the valorization of biomass towards platform chemicals and added value products is part of this new strategy. Lignocellulosic biomass is a promising feedstock as it consists of cellulose, hemicelluloses and lignin. Glucose is the building block of cellulose and can be used beyond the production of ethanol for the production of hydroxymethylfurfural⁵,⁶, i-butene⁷ or Sorbitol⁸. Hemicellulose building block is xylan, precursor of xylose that can be converted into furfural,⁶ or xylitol among others. Apart from sweeteners, Xylitol and Sorbitol are considered in the production of dietetic foods to diabetics because the non-insulin dependent metabolic pathway. They can be used also in pharmaceutical applications (mainly as a carrier), the cosmetics industry (as an emulsion stabilizer), as moisturizer, texturizer and softener⁹. The US department of energy^{10,11} lists Xylitol and Sorbitol as top 12 high value-added building block intermediate chemicals that can be produced from renewable biomass resources, while the EU has included them both as part of the map of potential value chains based on sugars¹² due to the fact that there already exist commercial markets¹³ with the potential to replace petrochemicals¹⁴

The chemical synthesis of sorbitol has been evaluated from glucose via catalytic hydrogenation,^{15, 16} or from the fermentation of fructose^{17, 18} produced via glucose isomerization.^{19, 20} In addition techno-economic studies have been performed to evaluate a biorefinery that uses lignocellulosic residues for the production of sorbitol, without considering the use of the hemicellulose.²¹ Separately, the xylitol synthesis yield has been evaluated via xylose fermentation²² as well as hydrogenation.²³ The technoeconomic analysis comparing both synthetic paths has been presented by Mountraki,²⁴ while biorefineries based on sugarcane lignocellulosic materials towards the production of xylitol, citric acid and glutamic acids have also been presented²⁵. However, lignocellulosic biomass contains the building blocks for the production of both products simultaneously, and so far no biorefinery considering the production of both has been analyzed.

In this work a mathematical optimization approach has been applied for the systematic comparison of synthesis routes for the simultaneous production of xylitol and sorbitol from biomass. The study allows optimizing the operating conditions of the different units by including surrogate models for all major transformations based

on experimental data. The rest of the work is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the description of the superstructure of the alternatives. Section 3 describes the models developed for each one of the steps and technologies. Section 4 shows the solution procedure. In Section 5 the major results of the work are presented including the process design and the economic evaluation of all the pretreatments and synthetic routes applied to switchgrass and biomass of agricultural and forestry origin. A cost comparison is also included using the biomass of optimal composition. Section 6 summarizes the conclusions of the work.

2. Overall Process Description

The superstructure used for process synthesis is shown in Figure 1. Biomass must follow a size reduction step before pretreatment. There is a large number of alternative pre-treatments.^{2, 26, 27, 28} The ones more widely used are (1) steam explosion-dilute acid (H_2SO_4) pretreatment,^{1, 29, 30, 31} and (2) ammonia fiber explosion (AFEX).^{27, 32, 33} Sorbitol can be produced from glucose while hemicelluloses are used for the production of xylitol.⁷ Thus, once the lignocellulosic structure of biomass is broken down, the cellulose and hemicelluloses are separated. Between both pretreatments only dilute acid pretreatment allows releasing xylose from hemicellulose. The AFEX pretreated biomass requires further hydrolysis at 50°C. In this case only the xylan is hydrolysed by using an enzyme, xylanase, to promote the degradation. Similar considerations have been used in previous works as the showed by Aristizábal and Gomez.³⁴ Cellulose is to be hydrolyzed at 45-50°C for 3 days to obtain glucose^{30, 35, 36, 37}.

Glucose and xylose may follow two different pathways to produce sorbitol and xylitol, fermentation and catalytic synthesis. Xylitol can be produced via fermentation using bacteria *Candida guilliermondii*³⁸, adjusting the operating conditions at 30°C and 1 bar of pressure with a residence time from 35 h to over 100 h²⁴. Sorbitol fermentative production follows two steps: (1) an isomerization stage from glucose to fructose, which is carried out by *Streptomyces sp.* at 70°C,²⁰ and (2) fructose fermentation to sorbitol. Xylitol catalytic production is performed in a three phase stirred tank reactor operating between 100-120 °C and 40-60 bar for 60-241 minutes.³⁹ The reaction uses Ru as catalyst supported generally over NiO, TiO₂, activated carbon or zeotype^{40, 41, 42}. Sorbitol production follows a similar route. The reaction is carried out also in a three phase stirred reactor

employing Ru modified particles^{16, 43, 44}. The operating conditions are between 100-140 °C, 40-60 bar¹⁶ for 60-240 min.

The purification process is performed using two parallel multieffect evaporator trains, one per product. For the final products to crystallize, waster is evaporated saturating the xylitol and sorbitol solutions. Commercial steam is used only in the first effect.

Fig 1. Superstructure for the renewable production of xylitol and sorbitol.

3. Mathematical modelling

All the operations in the production of renewable xylitol and sorbitol from switchgrass are modelled with mass and energy balances, experimental yields, thermodynamic and chemical equilibrium and rules of thumb⁴⁵. To model the pretreatments surrogate models are developed using data from experiments or rigorous simulations of the units, ammonia recovery and catalytic xylitol production.

The superstructure is mathematically formulated in terms of temperatures, total and component mass flows, and component mass fractions. The components in the system are included in set $J = \{ \text{Water, H}_2, \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{CaO, Ammonia, Protein, Cellulose, Hemi-Cellulose, Glucose, Xylose, Lignin, Ash, CO}_2, \text{O}_2, \text{Cells, Glycerol, Succinic acid, Acetic acid, Lactic acid, gypsum, Ethanol, Xylitol, Sorbitol} \}$.

3.1.Pretreatment

The main objective of the pretreatment consists of breaking down the raw material. The challenge with lignocellulosic biomass is the complex plant structure. It consists of a matrix of lignin. Within this skeleton, there is a structure formed by cellulose and hemicellulose, polymers consisting mainly of glucose and xylose linked by o-glycosidic bonds. For the base case, switchgrass is considered as raw material, a native species in the Eastern part of the United States. We can assume a typical composition at the ranges of 15-20 % moisture, 25-40% Cellulose, 20-30 % Hemicellulose, 15-25 % Lignin and 5.55% Ash. The feedstock is washed and its size is reduced by grinding. This pathway is more effective^{2,46}. Both stages, washing and grinding, are considered only in terms of energy consumption ($162 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{t}^{-1}$)⁴⁶ and cost analysis since they do not change the composition of the feedstock. Next, the two alternative pretreatments indicated above, dilute acid pretreatment and AFEX, are analyzed comparing their yield towards structure degradation.^{27, 47, 48, 49, 50}

Ammonia fiber explosion (AFEX): This method treats the lignocellulosic biomass with a solution of ammonia at medium-high temperatures and high pressures to break the complex matrix of lignin. To avoid the possible environmental hazards and to reduce the costs of operation, it is necessary to recover the ammonia. The slurry stream rich in water and polymers is sent to an enzymatic process to release the sugars.^{27, 32, 33, 51}. Garlock et al.⁵¹ evaluated the yield of this pretreatment for different species of switchgrass. The set of experiments developed studied the effect of the ammonia ratio ($\text{kg} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$ of biomass) and the water load, the operating

temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the contact time (min) at 2.1 MPa on the yield of sugars. This operation is carried out in batch mode. To ensure continuous operation, additional reactors in parallel with storage tanks are required.^{27, 52} The slurry containing ammonia is sent to a distillation column that operates typically at 3 bar and 140°C to avoid ammonia decomposition.^{29, 53} The pressure may be raised up to 5 bar as long as the amount of ammonia in the slurry is present in traces. In order to obtain the feed, reboiler and condenser temperatures, as well as the purity and the recovery yield as a function of feed composition in ammonia and the operating pressure, a surrogate model developed in previous work⁵⁴ from a rigorous simulation of the column in ChemCAD is used. The recovered ammonia is absorbed in water to pressurize a liquid and recycle it. This point is key towards the economic savings, avoiding the compression of ammonia gas. Only 0.5% of the total ammonia is lost in the slurry and can be used as a nutrient in the fermentations downstream.⁵² Ammonia make-up is thus fed to the system continuously.

After that we can consider, based on experimental results, that glucose monomer is available in the broth. It will not be the molecule of glucose until the hydrolysis in which the monomer is hydrated, but for the sake of reducing the number of components, a dehydrated glucose is obtained that will be hydrated later on. Xylose is produced from the pretreated biomass via specific hydrolysis in BR1 shown in Figure 2.⁵⁴ The complete model and the operational conditions are summarized in *Supplementary Material, AFEX pretreatment*.

Fig 2. Scheme of the AFEX Pretreatment

Dilute acid: This pretreatment uses sulfuric acid and steam explosion to degrade the lignocellulosic structure of the biomass, see Figure 3. Experimental data on the performance of this pretreatment have been presented in the form of response surface models^{55, 56, 57} and mechanistic kinetics.⁵⁸ The first approach is more convenient for process synthesis. The yield towards sugars release from biomass depends on the operating temperature, the concentration of the acid, the residence time and the enzyme amount used, per gram of glucan, in the hydrolysis stage.⁵⁷ We consider that, as in the previous case, the glucose monomer is generated at this stage but it will be hydrated in the hydrolysis stage to obtain the sugar molecule. The xylose is obtained directly to be used in catalytic or fermentation process. Using the experimental data provided in Shi's paper⁵⁷, surface of response surrogates are developed to estimate the yield of the glucose and xylose released⁵⁸.

Next a flash (Flash 1) reduces the water content of the slurry, reducing water consumption and providing energy to the process. The mechanical separation (MecSep 2) allows separating the slurry. The solid phase is bypassed and the liquid phase is neutralized in Reactor 3 using solid lime, CaO.^{1, 30, 59, 60} Lime is a cheap chemical and the gypsum formed is easy to separate from the liquid medium⁶¹ using a filtration stage (Filter 1). The optimal time for this reaction is in the range of 3 to 10 minutes. The neutralized liquid stream is mixed adiabatically in Tank 4 with the biomass, and the resulting slurry is sent to hydrolysis. The cellulose needs a further step before it can be broken down into glucose but the xylose is ready to be used eq (1).

The complete model and the operating conditions are summarized in *Supplementary Material, Dilute acid pretreatment*.

Fig 3. Scheme of the DILUTE ACID Pretreatment

3.2. Xylitol and Sorbitol Production by fermentation pathway

The streams rich in xylose and glucose are mechanically separated in a centrifuge separation Mec Sep-1 and Mec Sep-3 depending of the pretreatment. After that process, two parallel streams are obtained, each of them with a different proportion of sugars, see Figure 4.

The production of xylitol from xylose fermentation is carried out in fermenter BR-2 by bacteria, immobilized enzyme systems, or fungus as *Candida guilliermondii*³⁸ adjusting the operating conditions at 30°C and 1 bar, with a residence time from 35 h to 100 h.²⁴ Heat exchanger HX-6 and pumps are used to control the temperature and pressure of this operation. The fermentation reaction is as follows:

During the process, other secondary reactions may also take place where Eq (2) is the most important, which consumes almost all the xylose reaching a conversion of 92%.²⁴ The unconverted xylose remains in the liquid phase. The hydrogen and oxygen needed are directly fed to the fermenter (Src-10 and Src-11 respectively). Ammonia as nitrogen source will also be provided (from Src-4) in the form of an aqueous solution to avoid the temperature increase due to large heat of mixing in BR-2, and to control the input xylose concentration to be in the range of 50-100 g per liter.²⁴ In this case, the optimal concentration is 100 g per liter because it allows to use the least amount of dilution water possible.

Fig 4. Detail of the Fermentation pathway

The production of sorbitol is carried out by fructose fermentation. The pretreatment releases glucose in the form of a dehydrated molecule. The hydrolysis step takes place to obtain glucose. The next operation consists in the isomerization to fructose,²⁰ which will be used by *Zymomonas mobilis* in its metabolic route to produce sorbitol.¹⁷ The optimization process of this step consists in optimizing the yield of glucose to fructose. The rest of glucose could be used to obtain a profit but generally is used as a nutrient for the microorganism, avoiding as well the secondary reactions. Glucose isomerization is described by eqs (3), (4) and (5).²⁰

$$K_{\text{isomerization}} = \frac{[\text{Fructose}]}{[\text{Glucose}]} \quad (4)$$

$$X_{\text{isomerization}} = \frac{[\text{Fructose}]}{[\text{Glucose}] + [\text{Fructose}]} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

The key factors in the isomerization are the temperature and the equilibrium isomerization constant, both related and shown in Table 1.²⁰

Table 1.- Range of operating variables for glucose isomerization

T (°C)	$K_{\text{isomerization}}$	ΔH (kJ/mol)
25	0.74	9196
40	0.92	9196
60	1.15	9196
70	1.3	9196

The increase in temperature has a direct effect on the increase in the equilibrium constant of isomerization. Therefore, higher operating temperatures imply higher glucose conversion, but Takasaki²⁰ stipulates temperatures of 70 °C as an upper bound because is the maximum temperature allowed for bacteria *Streptomyces sp.* Values above this limit give rise to the appearance of secondary reactions and a decrease in the enzyme or bacteria activity.

The stream resulting from the isomerization process is conducted to an ion exchange resins column (IER1), where a selective separation of sugars takes place. A stream rich in fructose (> 95%) is obtained.²² The glucose retained in the column resins can be recovered for reuse in the process, or it can be sold as high purity glucose becoming a source of additional process revenue. The stream enriched in fructose is sent to a fermentation process (BR-5) where the sorbitol production reaction is carried out, as shown in eq (6).

As in the xylose fermentation, it is also necessary to adjust the concentration of fructose in the fermentation medium to maximize its conversion. Chung et al. (1988)¹⁷ have studied the conversion of fructose to sorbitol achieved by *Zymomonas mobilis* as a function of some values of fructose concentration. Using those data, a correlation between fructose conversion and its concentration has been developed, eq (7). The graphical representation can be seen in *Supplementary Material, Xylitol and Sorbitol Production by fermentation pathway*.

$$X_{(\text{fructose})} = -1.40 \cdot 10^{-6} (\text{concentration}(\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}))^2 + 8.700000 \cdot 10^{-4} (\text{concentration}(\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1})) + 0.819 \quad (7)$$

The feasible range for the concentration of fructose is between 100 and 300 g/liter, values used to obtain a conversion above 90%. These conditions are necessary to determine the operating conditions in BR-5, since the fructose concentration determines the operation and size of the units downstream.

3.3. Xylitol and Sorbitol Production by Catalytic pathway

The streams rich in sugars can also follow a catalytic hydrogenation process in order to obtain xylitol and sorbitol, see Figure 5. On the one hand, the stream rich in xylose is directed to the solid-liquid separator S-L separator. In this unit, the lignin is removed, which is considered to be slightly wet, and whose purpose is to obtain pellets to be used as a source of energy for the process. We assume that the remaining hemicellulose is removed here with the lignin. The resulting stream must be heated up to 100-120 °C in HX-07, compressed up to 40-60 bar so that the catalytic hydrogenation reaction eq (8) can be carried out in the reactor (CR-1) for 60-241 min:³⁹

The classical method to obtain xylitol from xylose is carried out in a three phase stirred reactor employing as catalyst Ni-Raney⁶² or supported Ru modified particles.³⁹ Ni-Raney presents a lower price and a higher catalytic activity.^{63, 64} But the disadvantages of this type of catalyst are the leaching of nickel, fast deactivation and nickel dissolution.^{16, 40, 63} Thus, catalysts based on supported Ru are selected because they have a slower deactivation rate and high selectivity. The supports are generally NiO, TiO₂, activated carbon or zeotype^{40, 41, 42}.

The fresh hydrogen stream is fed to the reactor (CR-1) from the source (Src 5) at the same temperature and pressure as the xylose stream. An excess of hydrogen is fed to ensure complete conversion of xylose, the membrane MS-1 will be used. The excess of hydrogen is recovered and recirculated to the Mix-9 mixer.

To predict the yield of the reactor, experimental results from the literature³⁹ have been used to develop a model for the conversion as a function of the reaction time. While, the shape of the profile is sigmoidal and an equation like eq. (9) could be used.

$$X_{xylose} = \frac{d}{(1 + e^{(e+f \cdot \text{ReactionTime})})} + g \quad (9)$$

The best fitting was developed using Agustinson equation, eq (10):

$$\frac{\text{ReactionTime}}{X_{xylose}} = \frac{e}{d} + \frac{\text{ReactionTime}}{d} \quad (10)$$

This linearization model shows a good fit above 50% conversions. However, the operating conditions depend on the pressure and the temperature. A two stage fitting procedure is used to include the effect of pressure and temperature on the fitting parameters d and e. Table 2 summarizes the parameters d and e belonging to the fittings.

Table 2.- Fitting parameters d and e

P (bar)	T (°C)	d	e
40	100	1.4154	87.2875
	110	1.0572	11.8766
	120	1.0045	2.5342
50	100	1.3168	66.3309
	110	1.0179	4.0116
	120	0.9916	0.0533
60	100	1.1258	26.1553
	110	1.0288	6.0803
	120	0.9869	0.8522

The objective of the previous fittings is to determine the effect of the operating conditions on parameters d and e of the linearization model and to create a model that allows predicting the optimal operating conditions for the catalytic hydrogenation of xylose. The fitting of these parameters are obtained based on parabolas, shown through eqs. (11)-(12).

$$d = d_1 \cdot (T)^2 + d_2 \cdot (T) + d_3 \quad (11)$$

$$e = e_1 \cdot (T)^2 + e_2 \cdot (T) + e_3 \quad (12)$$

For each pressure the adjustment coefficients, d1 and e1, d2 and e2, d3 and e3, corresponding to the quadratic, linear and independent terms are obtained, respectively (summarized in Table 3). The fittings of these coefficients are shown in *Supplementary Material, Parameters fitting*, Figures S7-S12. The adjustment coefficients d1, d2 and d3 are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3.- Fitting coefficients d1, d2 and d3

P (bar)	d1 (bar ⁻²)	d2 (bar ⁻¹)	d3
40	0.0015268518	-0.3564497953	21.791809307
50	0.0013628024	-0.3160760678	19.2963948214
60	0.0002761889	-0.0677064946	5.1345819739

$$d_1 = -0,0000046128 \cdot (P)^2 + 0,0003987489 \cdot (P) - 0,0070425916 \quad (13)$$

$$d_2 = 0,0010399792 \cdot (P)^2 - 0,0895607578 \cdot (P) + 1,5620137517 \quad (14)$$

$$d_3 = -0,0583319918 \cdot (P)^2 + 5,0003378143 \cdot (P) - 84,8905163696 \quad (15)$$

The values for coefficients e1, e2 and e3 are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4.- Fitting coefficients e1, e2 and e3

P (bar)	e1 (min·bar ⁻²)	e2 (min·bar ⁻¹)	e3
40	0.3303424081	-76.912997503	4475.1631974317
50	0.291804531	-67.5108775881	3899.3733247795
60	0.0742351944	-17.5968962407	1043.4929867889

$$e_1 = -0.0008951573 \cdot (P)^2 + 0.0767103691 \cdot (P) - 1.3058206785 \quad (16)$$

$$e_2 = 0.2025593072 \cdot (P)^2 - 17.2901256531 \cdot (P) + 290.5971371624 \quad (17)$$

$$e_3 = -11.4004523267 \cdot (P)^2 + 968.4617221371 \cdot (P) - 16,022.5819653434 \quad (18)$$

Fig 5. Catalytic pathway

On the other hand, the stream rich in glucose is directed towards heat exchanger HX-16 adjusting the temperature between 100-140 °C, 40-60 bar¹⁶ before directing it to the catalytic reactor CR-2 .The reaction runs for 60-240 minutes. The synthesis of sorbitol from glucose is carried out in a three phase stirred reactor employing Ru modified particles.^{16, 43, 44} Catalysts based on Ni-Raney allows achieving a high conversion of glucose, but has the same disadvantages as the ones for the production of xylitol.

A fresh stream of H₂ at the reaction temperature and pressure is fed from Src-7 to CR-2. It is fed in stoichiometric proportions according to eq (19), but an atmosphere of excess H₂ is maintained, which is constantly recovered through the membrane MS-2. As in the case of the production of xylitol production, the excess hydrogen is recovered and recycled to Mix-10. Due to the lack of a profile of the evolution of glucose conversion with respect to temperature and pressure, the modeling of the catalytic reactor and the optimal operating conditions were based on data reported on the conversion of glucose conversion, above of 99.9%. data,^{44, 60, 65} and maximizing the amount of sorbitol produced simultaneously minimizing the costs associated with energy (see purification of xylitol and sorbitol).

Two heat exchangers, HX8- and HX-17, with auxiliary utilities control the temperature of the streams that are directed to the membrane modules in the event that they have a temperature above the allowed one.

3.4. Xylitol and Sorbitol Purification

Purification of xylitol and sorbitol is carried out using two sets of multi-effect evaporators: Evap1-Evap2-Evap3 and Evap4-Evap5-Evap6 for xylitol and sorbitol respectively, see Figures 6 and 7. The streams coming from the MS-1 and MS-2 membranes, rich in xylitol and sorbitol, are directed towards HX-11 and HX-20 where their temperatures are set depending on the solubility of the different sugars, eqs. (22-25), to improve the purification process.

Fig 6. Xylitol purification

Fig 7. Sorbitol purification

The operation of multi-effect evaporators is based on the use of commercial steam in the first one with the aim of evaporating water from the solution, and producing a steam that is used as heating agent in the next effect. The mass balance to the solute is as follows⁶⁶:

$$F_j \cdot x_{j,f,i} = C_{j,i} + L_j \cdot x_{j,l,i} \quad \forall j \in \{effects\}, i \in \{sugars\} \quad (20)$$

$$x_i = \text{Solubility of species } i \quad (21)$$

Where x is given by eqs (20)-(25) for each of the sugar and sugar alcohols:

$$x_{\text{Xylose}} = 0.0005 \cdot (T)^2 - 0.003 \cdot (T) - 0.9957 \quad (22)$$

$$x_{\text{Xylitol}} = 0.2102 \cdot (T)^2 - 6.0031 \cdot (T) + 201.47 \quad (23)$$

$$x_{\text{Fructose}} = 0.0016 \cdot (T)^2 - 0.0196 \cdot (T) + 3.1655 \quad (24)$$

$$x_{\text{Sorbitol}} = 0.1321 \cdot (T)^2 - 0.1578 \cdot (T) + 166.26 \quad (25)$$

The mass balance to water at the evaporation chamber of each effect is given by eq. (26)

$$f_{\text{water}} = \text{Vapor}_j + l_{\text{water}} \quad (26)$$

This condition is common for all sets of evaporators because the steam used in each effect is not in direct contact with the sugar solutions. The energy balance for the first effect is given by eq. (27),

$$H_{Sj} + H_{Fd} = H_{sj} + H_{Ej} + H_{Lj} + H_{Crj} \quad (27)$$

while for the following ones the balance becomes as in eq. (28):

$$H_L + H_{Ej} = H_{ej} + H_{Ej+1} + H_{Lj+1} + H_{Crj+1} \quad (28)$$

The enthalpies of the streams are calculated by the components considering enthalpies of formation, crystallization and solution of the solids.

$$H_{Fd} = \sum f_{di} \cdot (\Delta H_{formi} + \int_{T_{ref}}^T c_{pi} \cdot dT) \quad (29)$$

$$\text{where } F_d = \sum f_{di} \quad (30)$$

The rest of liquid streams can be calculated using eqs. (29)-(30).

H_E is calculated as the enthalpy of a superheated steam since it is generated in a solution whose concentration of sugars increases.

$$H_E = E \cdot (\Delta H_{form \text{ Wa}(liq)} + \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_{eb}} c_{p,liq} \cdot dT + \lambda(T_{eb}) + \int_{T_{reb}}^T c_{p,vap} \cdot dT) \quad (31)$$

The rest of vapor streams can also be calculated using Eq (31). H_{cr} is the enthalpy of the crystals and can be calculated with eq (32),

$$H_{Cr} = \sum c_{ri} \cdot (\Delta H_{formi(liq)} + \Delta H_{crysti} + \int_{T_{ref}}^T c_{pi} \cdot dT) \quad (32)$$

In the optimization it is very important to take into account that the solutions must go from one effect to the next saturated in the sugar to be recovered. For this, the constraint given by eq. (33) is used:

$$[\text{Sugar}]_i = x_i \quad (33)$$

Eq. (33) introduces a relevant term in the calculation since the operating conditions change depending on the solubility of the sugar. The model shows different solutions depending of the chemical route. The catalytic synthesis process presents a conversion of xylitol and sorbitol of almost 100%. In this case xylitol and sorbitol are exempted from impurities, allowing easier separations. However, the fermentation shows incomplete conversion of sugars where some amounts of xylose and fructose are swept downstream. Sorbitol is obtained from fructose, but each one has a different solubility, which allows to recover them separately without the risk of having impurities. In the case of xylitol, it should be noted that its solubility is larger than the solubility of xylose, so the presence of certain amounts of xylose in solution results in either the fact that the recovery of xylitol is lower or its purity decreases.

The temperature of the evaporating chamber is calculated using the ebullioscopy increment produced by the presence of the sugars in solution:

$$T = T_{eb} + \sum_i K_b \cdot m_i \quad (34)$$

$$T = T_{F_d} = T_L = T_C = T_E \quad (35)$$

where K_b is the boiling constant of water, 0.512 kg / (mol K) and m_i is the molality of each sugar. The pressure of each chamber is provided as a function of T_{eb} using Antoine's equation, eq. (36):

$$P_j = e^{\left(18.3036 - \frac{3816.44}{T_{eb} + 227}\right)} \quad (36)$$

The additional process constraints are provided by eq. (37) and eq. (38) .

$$P_j \geq P_{j+1} \quad (37)$$

$$T_j = T_{j+1} + 10 \quad (38)$$

4. Solution procedure

For simplicity, due to the presence of only one binary variable, the one related to the selection of the pretreatment, two nonlinear optimization models (NLP's) are solved involving 2700 equations and 3800 variables

each. The major decision variables are the operating conditions at the pretreatment reactors, feed ratios and temperatures of operation, the operating conditions at the synthesis, the split fraction, operating pressures and temperatures at the evaporators sets. This last one depends on the yield of each pretreatment as well as the biomass composition. The model is solved using a multistart optimization approach in GAMS with CONOPT 3.0 as the preferred solver. The objective function is the maximization of a simplified profit including xylitol and sorbitol production, and the thermal energy and hydrogen consumed due to the fact that it is the largest variable cost, eq. (39):

$$Z = P_{Xylitol} fC_{Xylitol} + P_{Sorbitol} fC_{Sorbitol} - P_{Steam} \sum_i \frac{Q_i}{\lambda} - P_{H_2} fC_{H_2} \quad (39)$$

Next, a heat exchanger network is developed⁶⁷ and an economic evaluation is performed to compute production and investment costs.⁶⁸ The production cost involves annualized equipment, chemicals (enzymes, sulfuric acid, CaO, ammonia, and the profit from gypsum), labor, utilities and raw material. The costs for utilities are updated from the literature, 19 \$·t⁻¹ Steam, 0.057 \$·t⁻¹ cooling water, Electricity: 1.7·10⁻⁸ \$·J⁻¹⁶⁹ and the base price for biomass is 100€/t. The estimation of the investment is performed with the factorial method.⁶⁸ First, the equipment cost is estimated with the mass and energy balances obtained from the optimization. The cost for the equipment such as heat exchangers, fermenters, tanks, distillation column, mechanical separation, filters, molecular sieves is updated from the values calculated using the correlations developed by the authors; see supplementary material of Martín & Grossmann (2011)³ and Almena and Martín (2015)⁷⁰. Next, the equipment cost is calculated as a function of the equipment cost, using factors of 3.15 and 1.4. These factors correspond with a facility processes fluids and solids for the physical and total fixed costs⁶⁸.

The economic study is followed by the analysis of the operation of different biomass types towards the production of xylitol and sorbitol.

5. Results

The facility is based on a feed of 18 kg/s of biomass, typically used in bioethanol production facilities and biomass processing⁷¹ using switchgrass as base case.

5.1.- Facility operation

Tables 5, 6 and 7 summarize the operating conditions of the pretreatments and synthesis paths and the purification of xylitol and sorbitol carried out in the evaporators.

Regarding the pretreatments conditions, the dilute acid process requires a higher temperature than AFEX, 180°C vs 110°C, that together with the presence of the acid allows to degrade a higher amount of hemicellulose to xylose. However, note that the acid can dehydrate the sugars into furfural and furans, inhibitors for the fermentation. We assume that it is not the case.⁵⁴ AFEX pretreatment requires higher pressure to break down the lignocellulosic structure of biomass and an additional stage for the hydrolysis of the hemicellulose that carried out in a fermenter at 50°C and 1 bar.

Within the synthesis routes, the catalytic process makes use of high pressures, close to 48 bar, and moderate temperatures, 100°C or higher. Optimizing process energy consumption and increasing xylose and glucose conversion allows operation at or near the lower limit of the operating conditions.^{16, 39} The fermentation process operates at mild pressure and temperature conditions, typically at 1 bar in all cases, using 30°C for the xylose and fructose fermentations, and 70°C for the isomerization of glucose to fructose. Fermentation results in obtaining lower sugar conversion rates due to the bacteria metabolism of *Candida guilliermondii*³⁸ and *Zymomonas mobilis*¹⁷, use of larger volumes to feed and increase the treatment time.

Table 5.- Pressure and temperature for the pretreatments

	Dilute Acid-Catalysis Hydrogenation		AFEX-Catalysis Hydrogenation		Dilute Acid-Fermentation		AFEX-Fermentation	
	P (bar)	T(°C)	P (bar)	T(°C)	P (bar)	T(°C)	P (bar)	T(°C)
Reactor 1	-	-	21	109.8	-	-	21	109.3
Reactor 2	1	180	-	-	1	180	-	-
Reactor 3	1	107.4	-	-	1	105.4	-	-
Hydrolysis of Hemicellulose (BR1)	-	-	-	-	1	50	1	50
Hydrolysis of Cellulose (BR3)	1	50	1	50	1	50	1	50

Table 6.- Pressure and temperature for the synthesis

	Dilute Acid-Catalysis Hydrogenation		AFEX-Catalysis Hydrogenation		Dilute Acid-Fermentation		AFEX-Fermentation	
	P (bar)	T(°C)	P (bar)	T(°C)	P (bar)	T(°C)	P (bar)	T(°C)
Catalytic Reactor CR1	46.86	104.43	47.92	100	-	-	-	-
Catalytic Reactor CR2	46.87	100	47.9	100	-	-	-	-
Fermenter BR2	-	-	-	-	1	30	1	30
Fermenter BR4	-	-	-	-	1	70	1	70
Fermenter BR5	-	-	-	-	1	30	1	30

The optimal operating conditions for each of the four alternative processes show the use of vacuum pressures to reduce the amount of commercial steam. Since all the processes work under approximately the same conditions of pressure and temperature, the comparison among the alternatives is performed based on the following ratios $\text{kg}_{\text{steam}}/\text{kg}_{\text{xylitol}}$ and $\text{kg}_{\text{steam}}/\text{kg}_{\text{sorbitol}}$ (Table 7). The catalytic synthesis processes use a significantly smaller amount of steam in the evaporators due to the higher concentration of xylitol and sorbitol. These processes show higher conversion of glucose and xylose. In addition, fermentation synthesis processes require the use of large volumes of cell cultures, which implies lower conversions of sugars and the use of larger amounts of commercial steam. The difference in the operating conditions is also due to the pretreatment yield. The dilute acid pretreatment has higher production rates of cellulose and hemicellulose than the AFEX pretreatment. As a result, the yield to xylitol and sorbitol is larger increasing the product concentration in the streams. Thus, the boiling point of the mixture increases, requiring the use of more steam in the evaporators since the operating pressure should not be further reduced. In addition, the fermentation synthesis processes require the proper concentration of xylose.³⁸ To achieve this, it is necessary to dilute the stream with water that is later removed in the evaporators.

Table 7.- Pressure and temperature for the evaporators

		Dilute Acid-Catalysis Hydrogenation		AFEX-Catalysis Hydrogenation		Dilute Acid-Fermentation		AFEX-Fermentation	
		P (mmHg)	T(°C)	P (mmHg)	T(°C)	P (mmHg)	T(°C)	P (mmHg)	T(°C)
Xylitol	Evap1	119.31	55.24	112.92	54.10	152.99	60.53	161.04	60.53
	Evap2	108.88	53.35	107.27	53.04	145.34	59.42	145.34	59.42
	Evap3	52.67	39.15	48.92	37.78	-	-	-	-
	$\text{kg}_{\text{steam}}/\text{kg}_{\text{xylitol}}$	0.23		0.20		7.17		7.15	
Sorbitol	Evap4	148.7	59.91	145.11	59.39	152.79	60.50	151.81	60.36
	Evap5	141.26	58.81	137.86	58.29	145.15	59.39	144.22	59.26
	Evap6	133.06	57.54	126.07	56.40	123.26	55.92	121.56	55.63
	$\text{kg}_{\text{steam}}/\text{kg}_{\text{sorbitol}}$	1.09		0.76		2.76		2.26	

Table 8 shows the main operating ratios used to compare the alternative production paths. It can be observed that the yield to xylitol and sorbitol is lower in the fermentation paths, due to the lower conversion achieved by the bacteria cultures. The best processes to obtain xylitol and sorbitol are designed using the

catalytic path. Within the catalytic process, the dilute acid pretreatment allows obtaining a larger concentration of sugars than the AFEX pretreatment, resulting in higher ratios of xylitol and sorbitol per kilogram of biomass and requiring less steam in their purification.

The hydrogenation based processes report steam consumption values one third to one fourth to that of the fermentation ones. However, the hydrogen consumption is 5 to 6 times larger. An environmental index to account for both contributions simultaneously based on the equivalent CO₂ emissions has been computed as follows: eq. (40), where EF is the individual environmental factor related to each of the contributions, which is 10.5 kg CO₂/kg H₂⁷² and 0.142 kg CO₂/kg Steam⁷³ respectively. Note that the feedstock is biomass, a carbon neutral source and the index is built for comparison purposes among the different alternatives. Table 8 shows the results. The larger energy consumption in the fermentation based processes results in higher emissions for both pretreatments. In addition, among dilute acid and AFEX, the lower hydrogen consumption shows lower impact due to the lower production of xylitol and sorbitol. Note that the emissions related to hydrogen correspond to the ones when it is not produced using renewable resources.

$$E = fc_{H_2} EF_{H_2} + fc_{Steam} EF_{Steam} \quad (40)$$

Table 8.- Major yields of the alternative production paths (abbreviations: F= From fructose; G= From glucose; *Indicates from the literature)

	Dilute Acid- Catalysis Hydrogenation	AFEX- Catalysis Hydrogenation	Dilute Acid- Fermentation	AFEX- Fermentation
X _{Xylose}	1	1	0.92*	0.92*
X _{Glucose} or X _{Fructose}	>0.999 (G)*	>0.999 (G)*	92.9 (F)	0.941 (F)
kg H ₂ / kg Biomass	0.007	0.005	0.001	0.001
kg H ₂ SO ₄ / kg Biomass	0.024	-	0.017	-
kg NH ₃ / kg Biomass	-	1.052	-	1.052
kg Xylitol/ kg Biomass	0.259	0.187	0.166	0.120
kg Sorbitol/ kg Biomass	0.282	0.231	0.142	0.102
kg Steam/ kg Biomass	0.505	0.587	2.013	1.374
E (kg CO ₂ /kg biomass)	0.145	0.136	0.296	0.206

5.2.- Economic evaluation

The economic evaluation is performed to both pretreatments and both synthesis processes, obtaining four alternative production paths, computing the production and investment costs. The detailed investment and

production costs for the alternative production paths are shown in Figure 8. Table 9 summarizes the total costs, which increase when the fermentation paths are selected. In general, the fermentation process working in continuous operation requires several fermenters operating in parallel. This, together with the need for larger volumes of flows to be treated and larger needs for steam used in the evaporators to concentrate the streams (Tables 7 and 8), results in larger costs. Regarding the pretreatments, AFEX involves higher costs than the dilute acid pretreatment in the case of catalysis hydrogenation due the need for a distillation column to recover the ammonia employed and an additional stage of hemicellulose hydrolysis, which explains the difference of 57% and 51% in pretreatment costs between AFEX and Dilute Acid Catalytic Hydrogenation (Figures 8 d and h). The fermentation paths feature the opposite behavior. This can be explained because the increase in the amount of sugars implies the use of more water to adjust the xylose concentration at the fermenter, requiring a larger number of fermenters and larger amount of commercial steam. This can be seen comparing the investment costs of heat exchangers (HX), which reach 46% and 58% for AFEX and Dilute Acid respectively (Figures 8 b and f). This can also be observed in the percentage of utilities of production costs, reaching values of 18% and 22% of the total respectively (Figures 8 a and c). From Figures 8 b, d, f and h it can be concluded that Dilute Acid pretreatment is cheaper than AFEX pretreatment.

Based on the major yields (Table 8) and lower investment and production costs (Table 9), the lowest cost process to obtain xylitol and sorbitol from switchgrass is the one that uses Dilute Acid as pretreatment and catalytic hydrogenation as a synthetic path.

Table 9.- Investment and production costs of the alternative production paths (abbreviation: E= Environmental Index)

	Dilute Acid-Catalysis Hydrogenation	AFEX-Catalysis Hydrogenation	Dilute Acid-Fermentation	AFEX-Fermentation
Investment (M€)	120.8	146.4	323.7	273.5
Production Cost (M€/yr)	18.7	22.9	45.8	37.8

Fig 8. Detailed productions costs and investment costs for AFEX-Fermentation (a and b), AFEX-Catalytic Hydrogenation (c and d), Dilute Acid-Fermentation (e and f) and Dilute Acid- Catalytic Hydrogenation (g and h).

5.3.- Biomass design and evaluation

5.3.1.-Evaluation of different raw materials

Once the dilute acid and catalytic synthesis are selected as the best pretreatment and synthetic paths, the analysis developed for switchgrass is applied also to evaluate other typical biomasses such as corn stover, forest residues like a birch, pine and spruce, hybrid poplar, sugar bagasse and wheat straw. The results are summarized in Table 10 with each biomass composition. The composition of water has a direct effect on the steam ratio and a larger amount of water the steam is needed to adjust the xylitol and sorbitol concentration increases. Furthermore, the increase in the fraction of water implies the increase in the amount of sulfuric acid used in the pretreatment. In the same way, the proportions of xylitol and sorbitol increase with a larger composition of hemicellulose and cellulose in the biomass, demanding a larger consumption of hydrogen. The environmental index remains for all of these biomasses in the range of 0.130-0.150 kg CO₂ /kg_{biomass} due to use of the same production process. The use of fermentation paths increases those values to above 0.20 kg CO₂ /kg_{biomass}. In general, the amount the lignin plays a fundamental role in the costs since it is biomass that cannot be transformed into products. In addition, an increase in the lignin content implies a higher energy consumption in the pretreatment and the increase in production and investment cost, in spite of the possible production of energy. This energy is estimated considering a boiler efficiency of 75% and 26,100 kJ per kilogram of lignin as an average value of heat of combustion. To be on the safe side, the credit out of this energy has not been included in the economic analysis. Based on these criteria and analyzing the data from Table 10, the biomass that offers the best results is corn stover, which is widely available in large parts of the world.

Table 10.- Major yields, investment and production costs for the different biomasses (abbreviations: W= water; C=cellulose; HC=hemicellulose; L=lignin; A=ash)

Biomass	Composition (%)					Production cost (M€/yr)	Investment cost (M€)	Product cost (€/kg)	kg Xylitol/ kg Biomass	kg Sorbitol/ kg Biomass	kg H ₂ SO ₄ / kg Biomass	kg H ₂ / kg Biomass	kg Steam/ kg Biomass	Energy from lignin (kW)	E (kg CO ₂ /kg biomass)
	W	C	HC	L	A										
Switchgrass	18.62	31.98	25.15	18.40	5.85	18.7	120.8	0.283	0.259	0.282	0.024	0.007	0.505	67,495	0.145
Corn stover	16.95	41.05	31.39	6.34	4.27	16.3	111.7	0.220	0.323	0.361	0.023	0.009	0.386	25,663	0.146
Birch (Forest Residue)	3.80	43.90	28.90	20.20	3.20	19.2	124.8	0.225	0.297	0.386	0.021	0.009	0.350	74,228	0.140
Pine (Forest Residue)	5.00	40.70	26.90	27.00	4.00	20.4	129.6	0.244	0.323	0.358	0.021	0.008	0.353	97,973	0.134
Spruce (Forest Residue)	2.00	42.00	27.30	27.40	1.30	20.5	130.1	0.238	0.281	0.370	0.023	0.008	0.347	99,421	0.135
Hybrid poplar	6.91	50.80	26.20	15.50	5.90	18.4	121.5	0.213	0.270	0.447	0.022	0.009	0.357	57,374	0.144
Sugar Bagasse	7.00	41.00	30.10	21.20	7.00	19.4	125.5	0.230	0.310	0.361	0.022	0.008	0.361	77,889	0.140
Wheat Straw	8.43	40.26	30.56	16.52	4.23	18.5	121.5	0.228	0.315	0.354	0.022	0.008	0.364	61,446	0.140

5.3.2- Biomass design

As complementary objective of this work, instead of using a fixed biomass composition, belonging to a lignocellulosic feedstock such as switchgrass, the optimal flowsheet is used to determine the best composition within the typical ranges of hemicelluloses, cellulose and lignin for the simultaneous production. The resulting composition is compared with a database to determine the most suitable biomass. In this way the resulting biomass composition correspond to 15% water, 20% cellulose, 40% hemicellulose, 15% lignin and 5% ash. One that fits the best is sargassum algae (*sargassaceae*) with a composition of 20.48% cellulose and 43.19% hemicellulose. The production and investment cost for this biomass are 18.4 M€/yr (0.25 €/kg) and 120.5 M€ respectively. The breakdown in the costs are shown in Figure 9. Table 11 reports the major values for switchgrass and sargassum algae with slightly better values for the last of the two.

Fig 9. Dilute Acid- Catalytic Hydrogenation Free Composition productions costs (a), investment costs (b)

Table 11.- Investment and production costs comparative between switchgrass and sargassum algae

	Dilute Acid- Catalysis Hydrogenation switchgrass	Dilute Acid- Catalysis Hydrogenation Sargassum algae
Investment (M€)	120.8	120.5
Production Cost (M€/yr)	18.7	18.4
Xylitol (kg/kg _{Biomass})	0.26	0.41
Sorbitol (kg/kg _{Biomass})	0.28	0.21

To determine if this biomass is more promising than switchgrass, we compare the production and investment costs (Table 11). It can be seen that both biomasses yield similar values. The larger difference

between them is the ratio of xylitol and sorbitol produced per kg of biomass. The amount of xylitol and sorbitol produced are 0.26 and 0.28 kg per kg of biomass for switchgrass, while in the case of the sargassum algae, values of 0.41 and 0.21 are obtained, respectively. The difference in the market prices of xylitol and sorbitol (3900\$/ton and 650\$/ton)⁷⁴ suggests choosing a larger quantity produced of the product with a higher selling price. However, the environmental impact assessment plays an important role because it allows to determine the process with lowest CO₂ emissions, and therefore the one that uses the least amounts of hydrogen and steam. Thus, the key parameters are the larger amount of xylitol produced per kg of biomass and the environmental index. The differences also explains the choice of sargassum algae as the best biomass, and not the corn stover (Table 12).

Table 12.- Xylitol and sorbitol production comparative between switchgrass, sargassum algae and corn stover

	Dilute Acid-Catalysis Hydrogenation switchgrass	Dilute Acid-Catalysis Hydrogenation Sargassum algae	Dilute Acid-Catalysis Hydrogenation Corn stover
Xylitol production (kt/yr)	145	230	181
Sorbitol production (kt/yr)	157.6	116	202
Xylitol (kg/kg _{Biomass})	0.26	0.41	0.32
Sorbitol (kg/kg _{Biomass})	0.28	0.21	0.36
E (kg CO ₂ /kg biomass)	0.145	0.141	0.146

6. Conclusions

Xylitol and sorbitol production from lignocellulosic biomass has been evaluated within the integrated biorefinery concept. Four different chemical paths are considered for the production of xylose and glucose and the final products. The biorefinery is modelled using first principles and surrogate models for each one of the operations. The selected option is dilute acid as the pretreatment and catalytic hydrogenation as synthetic path. Assuming that no inhibitors are produced for a facility that produces 145 kt/yr of xylitol and 157.6 kt/yr of sorbitol, the investment adds up to 120,8 M€ for a production cost of 0.28€/kg. Integrated facilities operate at their optimum for specific biomass compositions. This framework also allows evaluating the best use of each biomass used depending on its composition, as long as the models for the pretreatments are valid. Within the biomasses considered, corn stover is chosen as the best option, resulting in a production capacity of 181 kt/yr of xylitol and 202 kt/yr of sorbitol, while the investment adds up to 112 M€ for a production cost of 0.22€/kg.

As a complementary study, the design of the optimal biomass was performed. Among all of components, hemicellulose and cellulose are selected because they are the sources of sugars. Thus, the optimal biomass is the one that provides the closest composition with an existing biomass and provides a lower environmental index. For this case, the optimal composition of those components obtained was 20% cellulose and 40% hemicellulose, finding the closest composition of 20.48% cellulose and 43.19% hemicellulose in sargassum algae (*sargassaceae*) biomass. For this biomass, 230 kt/yr of xylitol and 116 kt/yr of sorbitol are obtained, reaching an environmental factor of 0.141 kg CO₂/kg biomass with an investment of up to 120.5 M€ for a production cost of 0.25€/kg. Further validation of the process at pilot plant is necessary before actual industrial production using the concepts presented in this work.

7.-Nomenclature

a,b,c	Fitting parameters for ammonia recovery column operation
d,e	Fitting parameters for xylitol conversion
d ₁ , d ₂ , d ₃	Fitting coefficients to obtain d parameter
e ₁ , e ₂ , e ₃	Fitting coefficients to obtain e parameter
amonia_ratio	Ratio of ammonia added vs. dry biomass to AFEX pretreatment (g·g ⁻¹)
conc_acid_mix	Acid concentration at pretreatment in weight percentage.
C _i	Material cost (\$·g ⁻¹ or \$·W ⁻¹)
C _p _i	Heat capacity of component I (kJ/(kg·°C))
D _{i,k}	Flow of component I in distillate of column k
Dt:	Temperature increment
enzyme_add	Ratio of enzyme added to hydrolysis for acid pretreatment as function of the glucan (g·g ⁻¹)
E	Environmental index (kg CO ₂ / kg biomass)
EF _{H2}	Environmental factor for hydrogen (kg CO ₂ / kg H ₂)
EF _{Steam}	Environmental factor for steam (kg CO ₂ / kg steam)
C _{ri}	Flow of sugar i in crystal stream (kg/s)
f _{cH2}	Flow of consumed hydrogen (kg/s)
f _{cSorbitol}	Flow of purified sorbitol (kg/s)
f _{cXylitol}	Flow of purified xylitol (kg/s)
f _{di}	Flow of sugar i in evaporator feed (kg/s)
l _i	Flow of sugar i in solution flow (kg/s)
F _d :	Feed to multieffect column (kg/s)
ΔH	Reaction enthalpy (kJ/mol)
ΔH _{form i}	Formation enthalpy of component i at 25°C (kJ/kg)
H _{cr}	Crystals enthalpy (kW)
H _E	Vapor enthalpy (kW)
H _e	Condensated vapor enthalpy (kW)
H _{Fd}	Feed enthalpy (kW)
H _L	Solution enthalpy (kW)
H _S	Steam enthalpy (kW)
H _s	Condensated steam enthalpy (kW)
LoadAmmonia_water	Mass ratio between ammonia and water
m _(J, unit,unit1)	mass flow of component J from unit to unit 1(kg/s)
m _i	Molality of sugar i (mol/kg)
K _b	Ebullioscopy water constant (0.512 kg/(mol·K))

$K_{isomerization}$	Isomerization glucose constant
P	Pressure (bar)
P_i	Prices of component i (€/kg - €/kWh)
P_j	Operating pressure of evaporator j (bar)
P_k	Pressure of column k
$Q_{(unit)}$	Thermal energy involved in unit (W)
Q_{Bk}	Thermal flow in boiler of column k
Q_{Wk}	Thermal flow in condenser of column k
R	Reflux ration
ReactionTime	Reaction time in catalytic reactors CR-1 and CR-2
$T_{(Unit, Unit1)}$	Temperature of the stream from unit to unit 1 (°C)
T_{Bk}	Temperature in boiler of column k
T_{Ck}	Temperature in condenser of column k
time_pret (min)	Time for acid pretreatment
T	Operating temperature (°C)
T_{acid}	Operating temperature acid pretreatment (°C)
T_{afex}	Operating temperature AFEX pretreatment (°C)
T_{Cr}	Operating crystals temperature (°C)
T_{eb}	Ebullition temperature (°C)
T_E	Vapor overhead temperature (°C)
T_{Fd}	Operating feed temperature (°C)
T_L	Operating solution temperature (°C)
T_{ref}	Operating reference temperature (25 °C)
T_S	Operating steam temperature (°C)
T_j	Operating temperature in evaporator j (°C)
T_{j+1}	Operating temperature in evaporator j+1 (°C)
time_pret	Time for AFEX pretreatment (min)
water_pret	Ratio of water added to AFEX pretreatment function of the dry biomass (g·g ⁻¹)
$W_{i,k}$	Flow of component I in residue of column k
$W_{(unit)}$	Electrical power involved in unit (W)
x_i	Sugar i solubility (g/100 water – kg/kg water)
X_i	Sugar i conversion
yield	Yield of the pretreatment / unit

Symbols

λ	Latent heat steam (kJ/kg)
η	Separation ratio in column
\square	Concentration (mol/L-g/100 ml water-kg/kg water)

Appendix

Wa: Water
 CO₂: Carbon dioxide
 CH_{1.8}O_{0.5}N_{0.2}: Cells
 C₅H₁₀O₅: Xylose
 C₅H₁₂O₅: Xylitol
 C₆H₁₂O₆: Fructose-glucose
 C₆H₁₄O₆: Sorbitol
 CaO: Lime
 CaSO₄: gypsum
 H₂: Hydrogen
 H₂SO₄: Sulfuric acid
 NH₃: Ammonia
 O₂: Oxygen

Indexes

Supporting Information

Data on the development to models and fittings and results on the break down of costs for the different biomasses can be found in the supporting information. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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References

- [1].Aden, A.; Foust, T. Technoeconomic analysis of the dilute sulfuric acid and enzymatic hydrolysis process for the conversion of corn stover to ethanol. *Cellulose*. **2009**, *16*, 535-45.
- [2].Keshwani, D.R.; Cheng, J.J. Switchgrass for bioethanol and other value-added applications: A review. *Bioresource Technology*. **2009**, *100*, 1515–23.
- [3].Martín, M.; Grossmann, I.E. Energy Optimization of Bioethanol Production via Gasification of Switchgrass. *AIChE Journal*. **2011**, *57*(12), 3408-3428.
- [4].Karuppiyah, R.; Peschel, A.; Grossmann, I.E.; Martín, M.; Martinson, W.; Zullo, L. Energy optimization for the design of corn-based ethanol plants. *AIChE Journal*. **2008**, *54*(6), 1499–1525. doi:10.1002/aic.11480.
- [5].Kabir Kazi, F.; Patel, A.D.; Serrano-Ruiz, J.C.; Dumesic, J.A.; Anexa, R.P. Techno-economic analysis of dimethylfuran (DMF) and hydroxymethylfurfural(HMF) production from pure fructose in catalytic processes. *Chem. Eng. J.* **2011**, *169*, 329–338.
- [6].Yemis, O.; Mazza, G. Optimization of furfural and 5-hydroxymethylfurfural production from wheat straw by a microwave-assisted process Biores. *Technol.* **2012**, *109*, 215–223.
- [7].Marlière, P. Inventor; Marlière, P. assignee. Production of alkenes by enzymatic decarboxylation of 3-hydroxyalkanoic acids. United states Patent US20110165644 A1 2011 Jul. 7
- [8].Ribeiro, L.; Delgado, J.J.; Orfao, J.; Pereira, M. F. A one-pot method for the enhanced production of xylitol directly from hemicellulose (corn cob xylan). *RSC Adv.* **2016**, *6*, 95320.
- [9].Marques, C.; Tarek, R.; Sara, M.; Brar, S.K. Sorbitol production from biomass and its global market. *Platform Chemical Biorefinery, Future Green Industry.* **2016**, *12*, 217-227.
- [10].Holladay, J.; Bozell, J.; White, J.; Johnson, D. Top value-added chemicals from biomass. Volume II-Results of Screening for Potential Candidates from Biorefinery Lignin. **2007**. DOE Report PNNL 16983.

- [11].Werpy, T.; Petersen, G.; Aden, A.; Bozell, J.; Holladay, J.; Manheim, A.; Eliot, D.; Lasure, L.; Jones, S. Top Value-Added Chemicals from Biomass. Volume I- Results of Screening for Potential Candidates from Sugars and Synthesis Gas. **2004**. DOE/GO-102004-1992.
- [12].Final report for the European Commission Directorate-General Energy. From the Sugar Platform to biofuels and biochemicals, Final report for the European Commission Directorate-General Energy. **2015**. N° ENER/C2/423-2012/SI2.673791. V2.1 .
- [13].Gérardy, R.; Debecker, D.P.; Estager, J.; Luis, P.; Monbaliu, J.C.M. Continuous Flow Upgrading of Selected C2-C6 Platform Chemicals Derived from Biomass, *Chem. Rev.* **2020**, *120*(15), 7219–7347.
- [14].Dusselier, M.; Mascal, M.; Sels, B.F. Top Chemical Opportunities from Carbohydrate Biomass: A Chemist’s View of the Biorefinery. *Topics in Current Chemistry.* **2014**, *355*, 1-40.
- [15].Ribeiro, L.S.; Melo Orfao, J.J .de; Pereisa, M.F.R. Direct catalytic production of sorbitol from waste cellulosic materials. *Bioresource Technology*, **2017**, *232*, 152-158.
- [16].Van Gorp, K.; Boerman, E.; Cavenaghi, C.V.; Berben, P.H. Catalytic hydrogenation of fine chemicals: sorbitol production. *Catalysis Today.* **1999**, *52*, 349–361.
- [17].Chung, U.H. ; Rogers, P.L. The Simultaneous Production of Sorbitol from Fructose and Gluconic Acid from Glucose using an oxidoreductase of *Zymomonas Mobilis*. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* **1988**, *29*, 19-24.
- [18].Silveira, M.M.; Jonas, R. The biotechnological production of sorbitol. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* **2002**, *59*, 400–408.
- [19].Illanes, A.; Zuñiga, M.E.; Contreras, S.; Guerrero, A. Reactor design for the enzymatic isomerization of glucose to fructose. *Bioprocess Engineering.* **1992**, *7*(5), 199–204.
- [20].Takasaki, Y. Kinetic and Equilibrium Studies on d-Glucose-dFructose Isomerization Catalyzed by Glucose Isomerase from *Streptomyces* sp. *Agricultural and Biological Chemistry*, **1967**, *31*(3), 309-313.
- [21].Kapandji, K.K.; Haigh, K.F.; Görgens, J.F. Techno-Economic Analysis of Chemically Catalysed Lignocellulose Biorefineries at A Typical Sugar Mill: Sorbitol or Glucaric Acid and Electricity Co-Production. *Bioresource Technology.* **2019**, *289*, 121635.
- [22].Srivani, K.; Pydi Setty, Y. Parametric optimization of xylitol production from xylose by fermentation. *Asia-Pac. J. Chem. Eng.* **2012**, *7*(3), 280–284.
- [23].Rafiqui, S.M.; Mimi Sakinah, A.M. Processes for the Production of Xylitol—A Review. *Food Reviews International.* **2013**, *29*(2), 127-156.
- [24].Mountraki, A.D.; Koutsospyros, K. R.; Mlayah, B.B.; Kokossis, A.C. Selection of Biorefinery Routes: The Case of Xylitol and its Integration with an Organosolv Process. *Waste and Biomass Valorization.* **2017**, *8*, 2283-2300.
- [25].Ozudogru, R.; Nieder-Heitmann, M.; Haigh, K.F.; Görgens, J.F. Techno-economic analysis of product biorefineries utilizing sugarcane lignocelluloses: Xylitol, citric acid and glutamic acid scenarios annexed to sugar mills with electricity co-production. *Ind Crops and Products*, **2019**, *133*, 259-268.

- [26].Alvira, P.; Tomás-Pejó, E.; Ballesteros, M.; Negro, M.J. Pretreatment technologies for an efficient bioethanol production process based on enzymatic hydrolysis: A review. *Bioresource Technology*. **2010**, *101*, 4851–4861.
- [27].Sung, Y.; Cheng, J. Hydrolysis of lignocellulosic materials for ethanol production: a review. *Bioresource Technology*. **2002**, *83*, 1-11.
- [28].Taherzadeh, M.; Karimi, K. Pretreatment of Lignocellulosic Wastes to improve ethanol and biogas production: A review. *Int J Mol Sci*. **2008**, *9*, 1621-1651.
- [29].Kazi, F.K.; Fortman, J.A.; Anex, R.P.; Hsu, D.D.; Aden, A.; Dutta, A.; Kothandaraman, G. Technoeconomic comparison of process technologies for biochemical ethanol production from corn stover. *Fuel*. **2010**; *89*, 20-28.
- [30].Piccolo, C.; Bezzo, F. A techno-economic comparison between two technologies for bioethanol production from lignocelluloses. *Biomass Bioenergy*. **2009**, *33*, 478 – 491.
- [31].Zhang, J.; Li, J.B; Wu, S.B.; Liu, Y. Advances in the Catalytic Production and Utilization of Sorbitol. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res*. **2013**, *52(34)*, 11799–11815.
- [32].Alizadeh, H.; Teymouri, F.; Gilbert, T.I; Dale, B.E. Pretreatment of switchgrass by ammonia fiber explosion (AFEX). *Appl Biochem Biotech*. **2005**, *124*, 1133-1141.
- [33].Murnen, H.K.; Balan, V; Chundawat, S.P.S.; Bals, B.; Sousa, L. da C.; Dale, B.E. Optimization of Ammonia fiber expansion (AFEX) pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis of *Miscanthus x giganteus* to Fermentable sugars. *Biotechnol Prog*. **2007**, *23*, 846-850.
- [34].Aristizábal, V.; Gómez, Á. Biorefineries based on coffee cut-stems and sugarcane bagasse: Furan-based compounds and alkanes as interesting products. *Bioresource technology*. **2015**, *196*, 480-489.
- [35].Gregg, D.; Saddler, J.N. Bioconversion of lignocellulosic residue to ethanol: Process flowsheet development. *Biomass Bioenergy*. **1995**, *9 (1-5)*, 287-302.
- [36].Hamelinck, C.N.; Hooijdonk, G.V.; Faaij, A.P.C. Ethanol from lignocellulosic biomass: techno-economic performance in short-, middle- and long-term. *Biomass Bioenergy*. **2005**, *28*, 384-410.
- [37].Wooley, R.; Ruth, M.; Sheehan, J.; Ibsen, K.; Majdeski, H.; Galvez, A. Lignocellulosic biomass to ethanol process design and economics utilizing co-current dilute acid prehydrolysis and enzymatic hydrolysis current and futuristic scenarios. Golden, Colorado, 132 p. **1999**. NREL/ TP – 580- 26157.
- [38].Silva, S.S.; Roberto, I.C.; Felipe, M.G.; Mancilha, I.M. Batch fermentation of xylose for xylitol production in stirred tank bioreactor. *Process Biochemistry*. **1996**, *31(6)*, 549-553.
- [39].Ngoc Pham, T.; Samikannu, A.; Rautio, A.R.; Juhasz, K.L.; Konya, Z.; Wärna, J.; Kordas, K.; Mikkola, J.P. Catalytic hydrogenation of D-xylose over Ru decorated carbon foam catalyst in a SpinChem rotating bed reactor. *Topic in Catalysis*. **2016**, *59*, 1165-1177.
- [40].Gallezot, P.; Nicolaus, N.; Fleche, G.; Fuertes, P.; Perrard, A. Glucose hydrogenation on ruthenium catalysts in a trickle-bed reactor. *J Catal*, **1998**, *180(1)*, 51–55.
- [41].Hernández-Mejía, C.; Raja, E.; Olivos-Suárez, A.; Gascón, J.; Greer, H.F.; Zhou, W.; Rothenberg, G.; Shiju, R.N. Ru/TiO₂-catalysed hydrogenation of xylose: the role of crystal structure of the support. *Catalysis Science & Technology*. **2015**, *6(2)*, 577–582.

- [42].Luo, C.; Wang, S.; Liu, H. Cellulose conversion into polyols catalyzed by reversibly formed acids and supported ruthenium clusters in hot water. *Angew Chem Int Ed.* **2007**, *46*(40), 7636–7639.
- [43].Broekhuis, R.R.; Budhlall, B.M.; Nordquist, A.F.; Monolith Catalytic Process for Producing Sorbitol: Catalyst Development and Evaluation. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2004**, *43*, 5146-5155.
- [44].Kusserow, B.; Schimpf, S.; Claus, P. Hydrogenation of Glucose to Sorbitol over Nickel and Ruthenium Catalysts. *Advances Synthesis and Catalysis.* **2003**, *345*(1-2), 1-323.
- [45].Martín, M. *Industrial Chemical Process: Analysis and Design*; Elsevier: Oxford, U.K., **2016**.
- [46].Mani, S.; Tabil, L.G.; Sokhansanj, S. Grinding performance and physical properties of wheat and barley straws, corn stover and switchgrass. *Biomass Bioenergy.* **2004**, *27*, 339-352.
- [47].Kumar, P.; Barrett, D.M.; Delwiche, M.J.; Stroeve, P. Methods for pretreatment of lignocellulosic biomass for efficient hydrolysis and biofuel production. *Ind Eng Chem Res.* **2009**; *48*, 3713–3729.
- [48].Mosier, N.; Wyman, C.; Dale, B.; Elander, R.; Lee, Y.Y.; Holtapple, M.; Ladish, M. Features of promising technologies for pretreatment of lignocellulosic biomass. *Bioresource Technology.* **2005**, *96*, 673-686.
- [49].Sierra, R.; Smith, A.; Granda, C.; Holtzapple, M.T. Producing Fuels and Chemicals from lignocellulosic Biomass. *CEP.* **2008**, 10-18.
- [50].Tao, L.; Aden, A.; Elander, R.T.; Pallapolu, V.R.; Lee, Y.Y.; Garlock, R.J. Process and technoeconomic analysis of leading pretreatment technologies for lignocellulosic ethanol production using switchgrass. *Bioresource Technology.* **2011**, *102*, 11105–11114.
- [51].Garlock, R.J.; Balan, V.; Dale, B.E. Optimization of AFEX™ pretreatment conditions and enzyme mixtures to maximize sugar release from upland and lowland switchgrass. *Bioresource Technology.* **2012**, *104*, 757–768.
- [52].Holtzapple, M.T.; Jun, J-A.; Ashok, G.; Patibandla, S.L.; Dale, B.E. The Ammonia Freeze Explosion (AFEX) Process: A Practical Lignocellulose Pretreatment. *Appl Biochem Biotech.* **1992**, *28/29*, 59-74.
- [53].Sendich, E.N.; Lase, M.; Kim, S.; Alizadeh, H.; Laureano-Perez, L.; Dale, B.; Lynd, L. Recent process improvements for the ammonia fiber expansion (AFEX) process and resulting reductions in minimum ethanol selling price. *Bioresource Technology.* **2008**, *99*, 8429–8435.
- [54].Galán, G.; Martin, M.; Grossmann, I.E. Integrated renewable production of ETBE from Switchgrass. *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **2019**, *7*, 8943–8953.
- [55].Canettieri, E.V.; Rocha, G.J.M.; Carvalho, J.A.; De Almeida e Silva, J.B. Optimization of acid hydrolysis from the hemicellulosic fraction of Eucalyptus grandis residue using response surface methodology. *Bioresource Technology.* **2007**, *98*, 422–428.
- [56].Schell, D.J.; Ruth, M.F.; Tucker, M.P. Modeling the Enzymatic Hydrolysis of Dilute-Acid Pretreated Douglas Fir. *Appl Biochem Biotechnol.* **1999**, *77* (1-3), 67-81.
- [57].Shi, J.; Ebrik, M.A.; Wyman, C.E. Sugar yields from dilute sulfuric acid and sulfur dioxide pretreatments and subsequent enzymatic hydrolysis of switchgrass. *Bioresource Technology.* **2011**, *102*, 8930–8938.

- [58].Lavarack, B.P.; Griffin, G.J.; Rodman, D. The acid hydrolysis of sugarcane bagasse hemicellulose to produce xylose, arabinose, glucose and other products. *Biomass Bioenergy*. **2002**, *23*, 367-380.
- [59].Schell, D.J.; Farmer, J.; Newman, M.; McMillan, JD. Dilute Sulfuric Acid Pretreatment of Corn Stover in Pilot – Scale reactor. *Appl Biochem Biotech*. **2003**, *105/108*, 69-85.
- [60].Zhang, S.; Marechal, F.; Gassner, M.; Perin-Levasseur, Z.; Qi, W.; Ren, Z.; Yan, Y.; Favrat, D. Process Modeling and Integration of Fuel Ethanol Production from Lignocellulosic Biomass Based on Double Acid Hydrolysis. *Energy Fuels*. **2009**, *23(3)*, 1759–1765.
- [61].National Lime Association Using lime for acid neutralization. A proven solution! <http://www.lime.org>. Last accessed June **2012**.
- [62].Dasgupta, D.; Bandhu, S.; Adhikari, D.K.; Ghosh, D. Challenges and prospects of xylitol production with whole cell. *Microbiological Research*. **2017**, *197*, 9–21.
- [63].Yadav, M.; Mishra, D.K.; Hwang, J-S Catalytic hydrogenation of xylose to xylitol using ruthenium catalyst on NiO modified TiO₂ support. *Appl Catal A*. **2012**, *425*, 110–116.
- [64].Mikkola, J-P.; Vainio, H.; Salmi, T.; Sjöholm, R.; Ollonqvist, T.; Vayrynen, J. Deactivation kinetics of Mo-supported Raney Ni catalyst in the hydrogenation of xylose to xylitol. *Appl Catal A*. **2000**, *196(1)*, 143–155.
- [65].Romero, A.; Alonso, E.; Sastre, A.; Nieto-Márquez, A. Conversion of biomass into sorbitol: Cellulose hydrolysis on MCM-48 and D-Glucose hydrogenation on Ru/MCM-48. *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*. **2016**, *224*, 1-8.
- [66].Manteca, P.; Martin, M. Integrated facility for power plant waste processing. *Ind. Eng. Chem.Res*. **2019**, *58(15)*, 6155-6152.
- [67].Yee, T.F.; Grossmann, I.E.; Kravanja, Z. Simultaneous optimization models for heat integration—I. Area and energy targeting and modeling of multi-stream exchangers. *Comp. Chem. Eng*. **1990**, *14 (10)*, 1154-1164.
- [68].Sinnott, R.K. *Coulson and Richardson's Chemical Engineering Volume 6, Chemical Engineering Design*; Butterworth-Heinemann: Oxford, **1999**.
- [69].Pérez-Uresti, S.; Martin, M.; Jiménez-Gutiérrez, A. Estimation of renewable-based steam costs. *Applied Energy*. **2019**, *250*, 1120-1131.
- [70].Almena, A.; Martín, M. Techno-economic analysis of the production of epichlorohydrin from glycerol. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res*. **2015**, *55(12)*, 3226-3238.
- [71].Martín, M.; Grossmann, I. E. Optimization simultaneous production of ethanol and i-butene from Switchgrass. *Biomass Bioenergy*. **2014**, *61*, 93–103.
- [72]. Valente, A.; Iribarren, D.; Dufour, J. Prospective carbon footprint comparison of hydrogen options. *Science of the Total Environment*. **2020**, *728*, 138212.
- [73] U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (E.P.A.), Center For Corporate Climate Leadership. Emissions Factors for greenhouse Gas Inventories (**2018**).

[74].Rosales-Calderón, Ó.; Arantes, V. A review on commercial-scale high-value products that can be produced alongside cellulosic ethanol. *Biotechnol Biofuels*, **2019**, *12*, 240.

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